

Thermal Energy Storage Systems for Energy Efficient Buildings

What is TESS^{e2}b Project?

Innovative project that uses renewable energy and thermal energy storage

The TESS^{e2}b project aims to develop a **system for heating, cooling and sanitary hot water (dhw)** using thermal energy storage (cooling and heating) and renewables (solar and geothermal energy), controlled by an advanced management subsystem of intelligent energy, to be used in homes.

With this system aims to weatherize homes and prepare the AQS, **more efficiently, saving on energy and billing using renewable energy sources**. The system is intended to be more compact than traditional systems, allowing you to take up less space in the room and that is modular, in order to adapt easily to different dimensions and energy requirements of dwellings. Besides the management and control subsystem will enable easy use of HVAC system and DHW.

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